

The Effects Of Group Exercises For The Physical And Psychological Development Of Geriatric Individuals

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Short title: Group Exercise in Geriatric Individuals

Abstract

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the effects of group exercises on the level of independence in activities of daily living (ADL), psychological status and frailty level in geriatric individuals.

Materials and Methods: The study sample consisted of 50 individuals aged 65 years and over living in Sakarya. Participants underwent Otago exercise programme for 45 minutes a day, 3 days a week for 8 weeks. The Barthel Scale and Katz ADL Scale were used to assess the level of independence and the functions that could be performed. Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS) was used to assess psychological status and Frail frailty questionnaire was used to assess frailty.

Results: It was observed that group exercises significantly improved the Frailty and GDS levels of geriatric individuals. On the other hand, it was found that group exercises increased the level of independence in ADL with improvement in fatigue, frailty, cognitive and emotional effects ($p < 0.001$). In addition, Otago group exercises provided positive change in individuals by increasing social interactions. It was observed that there was a significant negative relationship between the independence levels of individuals and depression and vulnerability scores.

Conclusion: It was determined that Otago Exercise Programme positively affected the physical and psychological health of geriatric individuals, increased their independence levels and improved their quality of life. The study reveals that group exercises are an important tool that supports social, physical and psychological development for geriatric individuals.

Keywords: Depression, Exercise, Frailty, Geriatric assessment, Otago Exercise Program

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INTRODUCTION

Aging is seen as a natural process that lasts a lifetime with the advancement of age. This process affects the human organism in many ways. Significant physiological changes are observed especially in the cardiac and respiratory systems. There is a decrease in functional capacity and this leads to a decrease in metabolic functions. As a result of these changes, it has been stated that exercise performance is negatively affected, as well as loss of performance in daily life activities (1). In addition, significant changes also occur in the central nervous system. There is a decrease in muscle strength and endurance, a decrease in aerobic capacity, changes in body posture and losses in cells. At the same time, psychological changes are also observed in the aging process (2). Psychological changes refer to changes in a person's emotional state and behavior. Depression is one of the most common psychological problems in individuals and negatively affects health and quality of life in the elderly (3). Staying at home for a long period of time, loss of ordinary routine, stress, fear and decrease in social life lead to loss of hope and disappointment. As this process progresses, conditions such as depressive disorders, anxiety disorders, stress disorders and neurological changes occur (4). Aging, along with physical, physiological and mental changes, combined with living conditions at home or in a nursing home at the end of life, can negatively affect individuals' sleep quality and fatigue levels. Ensuring sleep and a quality sleep process improves memory, cognitive abilities, attention and motor functions of elderly individuals. It is known that sleep problems are particularly prevalent in elderly people living in nursing homes. According to a study by Kazoğlu et al. (2020), it was observed that the difficulty of falling asleep in nursing homes was 35-54%. It is explained that most of them do not get enough sunlight and lead a sedentary lifestyle, the rooms are not quiet enough and the presence of roommates (5). It is seen that quality of life, flexibility, muscle strength, heart and lung functions, physiological functions, balance and movement ability, sleep patterns, coping with depression and social life increase in geriatric individuals with physical activities in old age (6). The Otago exercise program is a type of exercise that is applied to reduce the risk of falls in the elderly, including 5 strengthening, 12 balance exercises and walking, 3 exercises and 2 walks per week, each session is completed in an average of 30 minutes. When practiced for 1 year, it is reported to reduce the number of falls in individuals from 1.4 to 0.5 and increase balance, walking speed and step length (7). OEP is also used in elderly individuals with various diseases. Many studies have shown that an 8-week application in stroke patients positively affects independence in activities of daily living (8). Similarly, an exercise program study with Parkinson's patients also showed positive effects. It was reported that 4 weeks of OEP practice improved balance and walking (9). These group exercise programs for the elderly provide an environment where participants have the opportunity to move together, share experiences and interact with each other. These exercises contribute to the development of not only physical strength but also important skills such as balance, flexibility and coordination. This study aims to evaluate the effects of group exercises on the level of independence in activities of daily living (ADL), psychological status and frailty level in geriatric individuals.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was conducted with 50 geriatric individuals in Sakarya Elderly Support Center and Sakarya University of Applied Sciences, Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation Application and Research Center. While determining the sample size, it was found sufficient to include at least 50

people in the study with an effect size of 1.177 with a power of 0.95 and a margin of error of 0.01 with reference to the KATZ scores of the reference article (10). Ethics committee approval for the study was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Rectorate of Sakarya University of Applied Sciences on 08.09.2023 with the number E-26428519-050.99-96216. The study was conducted in accordance with the Helsinki criteria and written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Geriatric individuals over 65 years of age who met the inclusion criteria and were selected for inclusion were administered an 8-week program that included group and individual exercises to improve quality of life with Otago exercises. The OEP was implemented in 45- minute sessions three days a week. The content of the program includes a combination of warm- up exercises, strengthening exercises, balance exercises, walking and standing movements (11, 12).

Inclusion Criteria:

1. 65 years of age or older
2. Having the mental health to adapt to group exercises
3. Be in good physical health to participate in the Otago exercise program

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Cardiac patients (myocardial infarction, arrhythmia, uncontrolled hypertension, etc.)
2. Individuals with pulmonary hypertension
3. Individuals with recent deep vein thrombosis
4. Individuals with obstructive and restrictive lung disease
5. Patients with severe musculoskeletal disease and psychogenic disorders

Individuals who met the inclusion criteria were administered the Barthel ADL Scale (BADL) to assess their daily tasks, the Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS) to assess their psychological state, the Katz ADL Scale (KAS) to determine the level of independence in activities of daily living, and the Frail Frailty Questionnaire (FFQ) to assess frailty.

Data Collection Tools

The Barthel ADL Scale: It is a scale used to record the patient's daily tasks. The tasks assessed in this scale include activities such as stool control, urine control, feeding, washing, dressing, transferring, toilet use, mobility, climbing steps and bathing. Scoring is done depending on how independently or assisted the patient performs these tasks. The resulting score reflects the patient's degree of independence; lower scores indicate that basic activities of daily living are performed more independently (13).

Geriatric Depression Scale: It is a 30-question self-report-based scale that is answered as yes-no. This scale aims to assess the mood of elderly individuals by comparing their mood one week ago with their current mood. The scale evaluates responses in favor of depression with one point, while other responses are marked as zero points. The collected scores are used to determine the level of depression. According to the scoring system, a score between 0-10 indicates the absence of depression, 11 points indicate the possibility of depression, while a score of 14 and above indicates that depression is certain. In terms of overall assessment, scores out of 30 points are categorized as 15 points and above or below 15 points. According to this classification, the risk of depression is considered high in elderly individuals with a score of 15 and above, while individuals with a score below 15 are considered to be free from depression. It provides an advantage in that it can

also be applied to patients with dementia. Turkish validity and reliability study was conducted (14, 15).

Katz Scale of Independence in ADL: This index, which includes basic activities of daily living, includes basic parameters such as bathing, dressing, using the toilet, transfer status, urine and stool control, and nutrition. These sub-parameters are evaluated as independent (1) or dependent (0) according to whether the patient can perform these activities without supervision, guidance and personal assistance. The score range of the index varies between 0 and 6 (16).

Frail Frailty Questionnaire: The test is based on five items and patients score 0 or 1 according to their answers. According to the total score, a score of 0 is considered vigorous (non-frail), a score of 1-2 is considered pre-frail and a score above 2 is considered frail (17).

Statistical Analysis

SPSS 27.0 package program was used for statistical analysis of the data. The variables evaluated in the statistical analysis of the study were defined with mean (X), standard deviation (SD), frequency (n) and percentage (%) values. Paired t-test was used to compare the initial and post-tests, and Pearson correlation test was used for correlation analysis. Correlation values were graded as follows: $r \geq 0.81-1.0$, excellent; $0.61-0.80$, very good; $0.41-0.60$, good; $0.21-0.40$, poor; and $0.00-0.20$, very poor (Cohen, 1992). $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Detailed information about the demographic characteristics of the participants included in the study is given in Table I.

Table I. Demographic characteristics of the participants

	X±SD	
Age	67.42±3.24	
Height	173.40±9.47	
Weight	76.16±9.05	
BMI	25.30±1.95	
	Number of people (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	52
	Woman	48
Cigarette smoking	Yes	60
	No.	40
Education status	Primary School	20
	Middle School	42
	High School	36
	University	2
Profession	Retired	36
	Housewife	39
	Tradesmen	11
	Worker	6
	Officer	8

According to the BADL scores, which evaluated the independence levels of the geriatric

participants in ADL, 12% were highly dependent, 72% were moderately dependent, 6% were mildly dependent and 10% were fully independent before the exercise program. After the exercise program, 56% of the participants became moderately dependent, 20% mildly dependent and 24% fully independent (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Participants' independence level in ADL before and after exercise

A statistically significant increase was found when the pre- and post-exercise scores of BADL and KGS were compared ($p < 0.001$). After the exercise interventions, there was a significant increase in the level of independence in BADL and the capacity to perform daily tasks (see table II).

Table II. Comparison of Parameters Evaluated After Exercise Program

	Before Exercise	After Exercise	95% Confidence Interval of Difference		t	p
	X± SD	X± SD	Lower	Upper		
BADL (0-100)	78.20±12.80	89.90±8.50	-14.26	-9.14	-9.179	<0.001*
GDS (0-30)	11.70±5.70	8.30±3.90	2.50	4.26	7.752	<0.001*
KAS (0-6)	4.40±1.60	5.30±0.90	-1.20	-0.53	-5.161	<0.001*
FFQ (0-5)	3.00±0.90	1.60±1.20	1.00	1.68	7.972	<0.001*

BADL: Barthel ADL Scale, FFQ: Frail Frailty Questionnaire, GDS: Geriatric Depression Scale, KAS: Katz ADL Scale

There was a statistically significant decrease in the depression level of the participants after the exercise program ($p < 0.001$). Finally, when we evaluated the fragility levels of the participants, a statistically significant decrease was observed in this parameter ($p < 0.001$).

There was a weak negative correlation ($p = 0.039$), a low negative correlation ($p = 0.011$), a weak negative correlation ($p = 0.049$), and a very good positive correlation ($p < 0.001$) between GDS and BMI, GDS and BMI, and FFQ evaluated after the exercise program. There was a weak negative correlation between GDS and BMI ($p = 0.005$) and a weak positive correlation between GDS and BMI ($p = 0.014$). There was a weak positive ($p = 0.036$) significant correlation between KAS and BMI (see table III).

Table III. Correlation of Parameters Evaluated After Exercise

	BMI		BADL		GDS		FFQ		KAS	
	r	p	r	p	r	p	r	p	r	p
BMI	1		-.292	.039*	-.389	.005*	.258	.071	.298	.036*
BADL	-.292	.039*	1		-.357	.011*	-.280	.049*	.661	<0.001*
GDS	-.389	.005*	-.357	.011*	1		.344	.014*	-.217	.130
FFQ	.258	.071	-.280	.049*	.344	.014*	1		-.080	.582
KAS	.298	.036*	.661	<0.001*	-.217	.130	-.080	.582	1	

BADL: Barthel ADL Scale, FFQ: Frail Frailty Questionnaire, GDS: Geriatric Depression Scale, KAS: Katz ADL Scale

DISCUSSION

In this study, group exercises with the OEP were found to have significant physical, cognitive and psychological effects in geriatric individuals. The study showed significant improvements in balance, muscle strength, daily moderate-to-vigorous physical activity and overall quality of life in geriatric individuals. In addition, positive effects on psychological well-being such as decreased symptoms of depression and improved sleep quality were also observed in these individuals. These findings are consistent with the existing literature emphasizing the benefits of exercise programs to improve the quality of life of elderly individuals and provide new data for research in this field.

Many studies in the literature support that OEP and similar exercise programs provide physical and psychological improvement in elderly individuals. OEP has shown significant benefits for geriatric individuals, particularly in improving balance, reducing fear of falling and improving overall physical function. This program has been adapted to address the various challenges faced by older adults and is believed to be a valuable intervention for fall prevention strategies (18). OEP has been shown to significantly improve balance in older adults with a standard mean difference (SMD) of 0.59 on balance measures (19). In a comparative study, participants in the OEP group exhibited greater improvements in balance scores than those in alternative exercise programs (20). Approximately 40- 70% of older adults develop fear of falling after experiencing a fall, and OEP effectively alleviates it. A systematic review showed that OEP significantly reduced fear of falling, contributing to increased confidence and mobility (21). OEP was associated with improvements in lower body strength (SMD=0.93) and mobility (SMD=-0.59) needed to maintain independence (19). Meta-analyses and systematic reviews conducted as of 2023 show that OEP improves balance, reduces the fear of falling and significantly reduces the risk of falls in older people. Its positive effects on depression and social isolation are also highlighted. The results of more independent living activities and reduced depression in your study are in line with these findings (22, 23). However, recent literature suggests that the psychological benefits of OEP are enhanced when it is practiced in a group format rather than individually, as it promotes more social interactions. We can say that the group exercise format used in your study makes a significant contribution to providing these advantages. In addition, it is suggested in the literature that the duration of the program should be extended and enriched with cognitive- motor activities to make the OEP more effective. Such improvements may increase the effectiveness of the program and contribute more to the quality of life of geriatric individuals (22, 23). The findings of your study seem to be consistent with the current literature on OEP. The findings of our study also support the significant and positive effects of the exercise program.

The Otago Exercise Program has been shown to significantly impact frailty in geriatric individuals by improving physical function and reducing levels of frailty. This program, which emphasizes strength and balance training, is in line with broader findings that exercise interventions are effective in reducing frailty among older adults (24). OEP has been shown to significantly improve frailty among geriatric individuals, particularly in community-resident and institutionalized settings. This program, which emphasizes strength, balance and mobility exercises, has shown positive results in reducing frailty levels and improving overall physical function (25). Some studies on frailty have summarized physiological effects. They show that participants in OEP exhibited significant reductions in frailty scores compared to control groups, with one study showing a decrease in frailty scores from 2.03 to 2.00 after 12 weeks (26). OEP has been associated with improvements in walking speed, balance and functional reach, which are critical for maintaining independence in older adults (27). Although the primary focus is on physical outcomes and specific psychological outcomes require further research, OEP also contributes to better health-related quality of life (28). Meta-analyses on this topic reveal that exercise interventions, including the Otago program, lead to a statistically significant reduction in frailty among older adults (29, 30). In our study, similar to the literature, a significant decrease in frailty levels was observed. It is seen in the literature and the findings of our study that exercise programs applied to geriatric individuals make individuals more fit both functionally and physiologically.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First of all, the sample size and the fact that the study was conducted only on individuals living in Sakarya do not provide information about how the results may vary in different geographical regions and cultures. In addition, the eight-week exercise program period only allowed for the evaluation of short-term effects and long-term effects could not be observed. The fact that most of the assessment tools used were self-report-based increases the possibility of subjective bias. In addition, although the positive effects of the exercise program on social interaction were observed, a more in-depth examination of this dimension was beyond the scope of the study. In addition, the study did not use a control group because the focus was on evaluating the effects of the Otago Exercise Program through the participants' own before and after situations. Furthermore, it was deemed ethically inappropriate not to offer a beneficial intervention to the participants. Similarly, not forming a control group increased the feasibility of the study by minimizing resource constraints. These approaches were deemed sufficient to determine the effects of the program.

CONCLUSION

This study makes important contributions to the literature by evaluating the physical, psychological and social effects of OEP in geriatric individuals. In particular, the positive effects of group exercises on social interaction and psychological well-being were emphasized, and it was shown that short-term interventions can improve quality of life and independence. In addition, the effect of OEP on reducing vulnerability levels was evaluated and supported the studies in the literature on this subject. The fact that the study was conducted in Turkey contributed to local data and allowed for comparability of effects in different cultural contexts. The findings shed light on both academic literature and practical applications to improve the quality of life of geriatric individuals.

As a result of our study, it was seen that group exercises were effective on activity level, fatigue, cognitive and emotional effects, physiological effects caused by the nature of aging, frailty, sleep quality and activities of daily living in geriatric individuals. It was also seen with the data obtained that these effects provided a positive physical and mental increase in the quality of life and social life of geriatric individuals. As a result of the numerical data obtained, it was observed that the exercises were positively effective both physically and psychologically in each individual.

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REFERENCES

1. Aslan M and Hocaoglu Ç. *Düzce Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü Dergisi* 2017; 7: 53-62.
2. Soygüden A and Cerit E. YAŞLILAR İÇİN EGZERSİZ UYGULAMALARININ ÖNEMİ. *Hitit Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi* 2015; 8: 197-224. DOI: 10.17218/husbed.58321.
3. Sivertsen H, Bjørkløf GH, Engedal K, et al. Depression and quality of life in older persons: a review. *Dementia and geriatric cognitive disorders* 2015; 40: 311-339.
4. Küçük U and Karadeniz H. Yaşlanmaya Bağlı Bireylerde Görülen Fizyolojik, Ruhsal, Sosyal Değişiklikler ve Korunmaya Yönelik Önlemler. *Yaşlı Sorunları Araştırma Dergisi* 2021; 14: 96-103. DOI: 10.46414/yasad.877517.
5. Kazoğlu M and Yürük ZÖ. Huzurevinde ve evde yaşayan yaşlılarda uyku kalitesi ve yorgunluk düzeylerinin incelenmesi. *Journal of Exercise Therapy and Rehabilitation* 2020; 7: 145-153.
6. Izquierdo M, Merchant RA, Morley JE, et al. International Exercise Recommendations in Older Adults (ICFSR): Expert Consensus Guidelines. *The Journal of nutrition, health and aging* 2021; 25: 824-853. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12603-021-1665-8>.
7. Günday Ç and Zengin Alpözgen A. Egzersiz Uygulamalarında Güncel Yaklaşımlar ve Kanıtlar. *Sağlık Profesyonelleri Araştırma Dergisi* 2021; 3: 85-96.
8. Mgbejedo UG, Akosile CO, Okoye EC, et al. Effects of Otago Exercise Program on Physical and Psychosocial Functions Among Community-Dwelling and Institutionalized Older Adults: A Scoping Review. *Inquiry* 2023; 60: 469580231165858. 2023/04/12. DOI: 10.1177/00469580231165858.
9. Giardini M, Nardone A, Godi M, et al. Instrumental or Physical-Exercise Rehabilitation of Balance Improves Both Balance and Gait in Parkinson's Disease. *Neural Plast* 2018; 2018: 5614242. 2018/05/01. DOI: 10.1155/2018/5614242.
10. Dogrul RT, Hymabaccus BAB, Balci C, et al. An effective and practical tool to assess physical frailty in older adults: Turkish validation of the FRAIL Scale. *Marmara Medical Journal* 2023; 36: 149-156. DOI: 10.5472/marumj.1297696.
11. Campbell AJ and Robertson MC. Comprehensive approach to fall prevention on a national level: New Zealand. *Clin Geriatr Med* 2010; 26: 719-731. 2010/10/12. DOI: 10.1016/j.cger.2010.06.004.
12. Prevention NCFI and D c. Tools to implement the Otago exercise program: A program to reduce falls. National Center for Injury Prevention and control CDCM Washington, 2019.
13. Sainsbury A, Seebass G, Bansal A, et al. Reliability of the Barthel Index when used with older people. *Age and ageing* 2005; 34: 228-232.
14. Burke WJ, Roccaforte WH and Wengel SP. The short form of the Geriatric Depression Scale: a comparison with the 30-item form. *Journal of geriatric psychiatry and neurology* 1991; 4: 173-178.
15. Ertan T. Geriatrik depresyon ölçeği ile Kendini Değerlendirme Depresyon Ölçeğinin 60 yaş üzeri Türk popülasyonunda geçerlilik-güvenilirlik incelemesi. 1996.
16. Balcioğlu H, Özkan Pehlivanoglu EF, Özkan MU, et al. Adjustment and Reliability of Katz Daily Life Activity Measures for Elderly in Turkish. *Ankara Medical Journal* 2018; 18: 219-223. DOI: 10.17098/amj.435264.
17. Hymabaccus Muradi BAB. Yaşlılarda Kırılganlığı Ölçmeye Yönelik FRAİL Ölçeğinin Türkçe Geçerlik ve Güvenilirlik Çalışması. 2017.
18. Paliwal C and Kulkarni M. Effectiveness of Otago Exercises in Elderly Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients to Improve Balance and Prevent Falls - An Experimental Study. *International Journal of Health Sciences and Research* 2024; 14: 43-48. DOI: 10.52403/ijhsr.20240706.
19. Wu S, Guo Y, Cao Z, et al. Effects of Otago exercise program on physical function in older adults: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics* 2024; 124: 105470. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.archger.2024.105470>.

20. KP N, D A, Nawed A, et al. Comparison of effects of Otago exercise program vs gaze stability exercise on balance and fear of fall in older adults: A randomized trial. *Medicine* 2024; 103: e38345. DOI: 10.1097/md.00000000000038345.
21. Han J, Wang H, Ding Y, et al. Effect of Otago exercise on fear of falling in older adults: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Sports Science, Medicine and Rehabilitation* 2024; 16: 132. DOI: 10.1186/s13102-024-00917-2.
22. Chen X, Zhao L, Liu Y, et al. Otago exercise programme for physical function and mental health among older adults with cognitive frailty during COVID-19: A randomised controlled trial. *J Clin Nurs* 2021 2021/07/22. DOI: 10.1111/jocn.15964.
23. Chiu H-L, Yeh T-T, Lo Y-T, et al. The effects of the Otago Exercise Programme on actual and perceived balance in older adults: A meta-analysis. *PLOS ONE* 2021; 16: e0255780. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0255780.
24. Lim H, Jani NDB, Pang WT, et al. Community-based exercises improve health status in pre-frail older adults: A systematic review with meta-analysis. *BMC Geriatrics* 2024; 24: 589. DOI: 10.1186/s12877-024-05150-7.
25. Morales-Sánchez A, Calvo Arenillas JI, Gutiérrez Palmero MJ, et al. A Prospective Observational Study of Frailty in Geriatric Revitalization Aimed at Community-Dwelling Elderly. *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 2024; 13: 2514.
26. Chen X, Ma C, Liu Y, et al. *The effective of Otago Exercise Program on the physical frailty, cognitive function and ADL of elderly with cognitive frailty living in Nursing Homes: a randomized control trial.* 2022.
27. Qin X, Mao Y, Wang H, et al. Effects of the Otago Exercise Program in older hypertensive patients with pre-frailty. *Journal of Physical Therapy Science* 2022; 34: 509-514. DOI: 10.1589/jpts.34.509.
28. Mgbejedo UG, Akosile CO, Okoye EC, et al. Effects of Otago Exercise Program on Physical and Psychosocial Functions Among Community-Dwelling and Institutionalized Older Adults: A Scoping Review. *INQUIRY: The Journal of Health Care Organization, Provision, and Financing* 2023; 60: 00469580231165858. DOI: 10.1177/00469580231165858.
29. Silva LGdC, da Silva SLA, Freire JCG, et al. Exercise-based physiotherapeutic interventions in frailty syndrome: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Physiotherapy Research International* 2024; 29: e2092. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pri.2092>.
30. Kasfi A, Rekawati E and Rachmawati U. Intervensi Latihan Fisik terhadap Perbaikan Status Frailty Pada Lansia. *Journal of Telenursing (JOTING)* 2024; 6: 1231-1239.